

Case for Support: UNPATH: Unpath'd Waters - Marine and Maritime Collections in the UK

1. Contribution to Towards a National Collection: Opening UK Heritage to the World.

The UK Marine Area extends over some 867,400 km², equivalent to 3.5 times the terrestrial land surface. The marine and maritime heritage of this vast area is exceptional and diverse. It encompasses submerged prehistoric landscapes, inundated monuments and settlements, wrecks and aircraft losses, maritime industrial and military complexes, coastal and intertidal archaeology, seaside resorts, ports and dockyards, with a proven potential to engage the public and address key research themes. The collections which record, locate, characterise and represent this abundance are remarkable. They are physical, digital, textual, graphical, artefactual, environmental, spatial and oral, but they are split between government organisations, commercial concerns, academic institutions, charitable foundations and trusts, museums and archives, and individual collectors. They are also in a fragile digital state and lack shared metadata standards, rendering interoperability and joined-up collection access impossible, and making the data associated with them far from FAIR. UNPATH will establish how to rectify this, providing a model for TANC.

Integration of the UK's marine historic environment collections requires a fully national effort by definition. UNPATH brings together the 4 UK government heritage agencies, 5 lead universities for marine research and digital humanities, 2 more supporting universities, the National Maritime Museum (NMM), the digital infrastructures of Archaeology Data Service (ADS) and Marine Environmental Data and Information Network (MEDIN), 2 major archaeological contractors, Museum of London Archaeology (MOLA) and Wessex Archaeology, and 9 other partners and collaborators from the charitable and commercial sectors.

Using this combined experience and expertise, UNPATH will show the way to unlock the UK's marine heritage data sustainably, permitting the first inclusive access to marine heritage records for all four UK nations, and opening these collections to the world via the European research e-infrastructure, ARIADNE and UKRI's One Ocean Hub. It will: extend scholarly and public access beyond the physical boundaries of Britain's rich marine heritage; deliver cutting-edge research that tells new stories and makes new connections across collections; develop and test new research-driven public-facing outputs; and create innovative virtual modes of accessing integrated collections to reach new and diverse audiences.

The proof of concepts provided by UNPATH will be applicable to wider collection interconnectivity challenges beyond the marine/maritime sphere. Our approach is not simply to develop technical methods, but to test those methods with audiences who can participate in their development. The resulting lessons will be immediately transferable to any number and type of collection, a critical component of the TaNC programme.

2. Project topics and questions

A high level summary of UNPATH's objectives, challenges and key outputs can be seen in the accompanying Timeline document. A key feature of our work packages is that they are designed to run concurrently and reflexively, informing and being informed by each other. These WPs form a coherent research arc aiming to characterise and organise the collections, resolve obstacles to cross-searching, apply these tools iteratively to real-world marine challenges and develop mechanisms to engage the public in co-designing new access routes.

WP1 Aggregation and Characterisation: How can we integrate the UK's marine heritage collections? WP1 will assess, enhance and aggregate the digital components of the UK's marine heritage collections; review the demands and capabilities of existing digital infrastructures; and enhance these to deliver the UK marine heritage collections to researchers and the public via human and machine-readable interfaces, providing broader lessons for TANC. We will develop appropriate data standards and cataloguing practices to achieve interoperability and deliver sustainable access routes and a primary data archive for UNPATH data outputs. This will lead directly to major improvements in national marine heritage inventories, including Coflein (Wales), Mariner (England), Canmore (Scotland) and, in due course inventories for Northern Ireland and, beyond UK waters, the Isle of Man.

WP2 Discovery: How can we transform our ability to search those collections? As detailed in the Technical and Data Management Plan, UNPATH will harness recent developments in Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning and build on work done in the TANC Heritage Connector foundation project, to enrich sparse data, increase interoperability and enable a diversity of search options. It will do this through adopting a low-shot/zero-shot approach to ML leveraging the assets created in WP1 via named entity recognition to open linked data. In addition, computer vision (object detection) and increased spatial/temporal awareness/visualisation will be explored within the cases studies detailed in WP3. This will enable distinct modes of discovery and recovery (text, image, 3D shape, sound, spatial, temporal).

Three specific marine research themes will test the infrastructure developed in WP1 and WP2 through separate and specific research objectives in geographically discrete sample areas:

WP3.1 People and the Sea: How can we enhance the significance of submerged and displayed wrecks? WP3.1 will use a sample of submerged Protected Wrecks (and nearby unprotected wrecks) in the English Channel (The Needles, *Mary Rose* and *Holland 5*) and displayed wrecks (*Mary Rose* and *Holland 1*) by employing new stakeholder processes for elevating the significance of underwater wrecks in relation to displayed wrecks. Approaches will test the capacity of connected collections, including wreck site surveys, recovered artefacts, documentary records and scientific samples, to engage audiences in co-creating new narratives and innovative ways of engaging with the wrecks. We aim to evaluate these novel approaches in enhancing public availability of wreck databases, serving as proof of concept for accessing other wreck sites and developing strategies for Protected and unprotected wrecks.

WP3.2 Science and the Sea: How can we use collections to identify located wrecks and improve their management? Using an Irish Sea pilot, this WP will demonstrate how greater connectivity between disparate collections of marine scientific collections and datasets can reveal identities and enable more effective heritage management of shipwrecks based on better understanding of their condition and long-term integrity. We will link a collection of high-resolution multibeam sonar surveys from >100 incorrectly identified or unknown wreck sites in the Irish Seas to other collections (shipping and naval archives, vessel plans, insurance records, personal correspondence and photographs etc), which will transform the value of historical assets whose research access is limited typically to vessel names and location of loss data. This will also provide strong baseline data for decision-making regarding newly identified wrecks of high historical significance. We will also dissolve boundaries with natural science collections (e.g. site-related geophysical and hydrodynamical/sediment transport models and marine ecological material to enable site-specific assessments on localised site conditions, integrity and sustainability of the national collection of shipwrecks.

WP3.3 Lands beneath the Sea: How can we open access to complex collections representing submerged ancient landscapes? WP3.3 will pioneer a method of accessing complex digital scientific collections relating to the underlying processes that created the archives representing the inundated prehistoric North Sea landscape known as Doggerland. These processes link users, data and unifying concepts between different datasets, including evidence for climate change and rising sea levels. Process-led access models are largely untried as a method, so a bespoke computer simulation will be created to allow users to experience the dramatically changing world which created the data collections, providing a clearer, more comprehensible, and interactive method of engaging with them which otherwise may seem sterile or impenetrable. The value of this research in connecting collections will lie not only in enhancing researcher and public access to an otherwise entirely occluded prehistoric landscape, but also in its ability to support far more accurate predictive models of likely archaeological potential in an area set to see massive exploitation for renewables in the coming decades.

WP4. Designing, Connecting, Immersing: How can we co-design and co-create research and engagement access for new audiences? As TaNC recognises, there is insufficient cross-disciplinary and cross-collection research use of the datasets, there is not enough public access, including online access and current audiences are neither diverse nor drawing benefit from the datasets. WP4 will address these issues by co-designing novel interfaces with integrated

maritime datasets (natural and cultural) specifically through the use of immersive systems, through three user-group case studies (see WP5). Between them, they will test: (1) What new affordances do integrated maritime datasets offer cross-disciplinary researchers? (2) Can modes of navigation be co-designed that counter the complexity of multiple datasets, from multiple sources and in multiple formats (2D/3D) which work for both research and public audiences? (3) Can we reach audiences that do not traditionally engage with these data but could directly participate in the design of access modes that encourage their future engagement? (4) Can the technical challenges posed by User Generated Pathways through the UNPATH datasets be meaningfully addressed via multi-modal immersive interfaces (i.e. delivered as full immersive systems, but also via e.g. desktop and mobile devices)? WP4 will adopt an iterative design process, which means that foundational elements can be co-developed independently of each other and in close collaboration with other work packages, so search mechanisms, user interface, and integration design can focus defined datasets with others being added as integration methodologies are developed as part of the UNPATH flowline. We will reach new audiences, and, crucially, engage with them in new ways, by developing the concept of 'curated pathways' through datasets and User Generated Pathways, both potentially very powerful engagement tools. This approach will throw up surprising routes through the data with stories emerging that might not be obvious to researchers immersed in specific and traditional ways of approaching these collections.

WP5. Engaging and Evaluating Audiences. WP5 links the work packages together to create measurable outcomes from maritime datasets, for targeted audiences, via the production of co-designed outputs. Whilst WPs1-3 are focused on priming the data and their supporting infrastructures to be effectively deployed by diverse users, and WP4 explores novel ways of interaction with their results, WP5 will underpin these efforts by identifying, engaging with, and evaluating impacts on these users. WP5 adopts a five-part approach to: (1) discover shared values for the project (and to guide audience-focused work) in line with the Digital Culture Charter, as well as metrics by which the project holds itself accountable to the values; (2) conduct audience mapping, building on the shared values to specifically identify and articulate a programme to ensure representation of three key target user-groups: non-coastal (inland) communities who do not identify with the sea; visually-impaired publics; and cross-disciplinary natural science and cultural researchers; (3) facilitate co-design and consultation with these audiences (qv WP4) and assess the efficacy and inclusiveness of the co-design approach; (4) facilitate testing and evaluating of the pilot designs that emerge through the interaction of WPs3&4 with our target audiences; and (5) coordinate and evaluate an exhibition programme of the final designs, including enrolment of other museums partners and industrial and 3rd sector collaborating organisations into the programme to connect with their existing initiatives. Here several centenary opportunities may be capitalised on: the 40th Anniversary of the raising of the *Mary Rose* (1982), the 50th Anniversary of the *Protection of Wrecks Act* (1973) for England and Wales and the bicentenary of the RNLi (c.1824). The research aims to reveal the emerging impacts of the project's outputs on its core beneficiaries: environmental and heritage organisations – including evidence of use in informed decision making; evidence of increased use of associated resources of UNPATH partners (e.g. CITIZAN app; *Mary Rose* visits); research communities – including evidence of application to current marine heritage management, evidence of materialisation of novel research agendas or consortia; and wider public audiences – including evidence of learning and social outcomes generated from WPs 3 and 4.

3. Partnerships and Collaborations

UNPATH's core partners are the Universities of Bangor, Bradford, Glasgow School of Art, Portsmouth, Southampton and York, and the IROs of Historic England, Historic Environment Scotland, MOLA, and NMM. The Universities of St Andrews and Ulster are in support. UNPATH is supported explicitly by the heritage agencies of all four UK governments. It includes representatives of all UK national marine heritage management datasets/ collections (Historic England, Historic Environment Scotland, The Royal Commission on Ancient and Historical Monuments in Wales, and the N. Ireland Dept of Communities Historic Environment Division) and, as Partners, Manx National Heritage and the Marine Management Organisation (MMO). The NMM provides a link to the UK Maritime Heritage Forum, and the Maritime Heritage Network and we received written support from National Museums Northern Ireland. The ADS, the only UK Digital

Repository for heritage data with the Core Trust Seal, and MEDIN are both Co-Is. Lloyd's Register Foundation with its extensive collections is a Partner, as is the Protected Wrecks Association which represents formal Licensees who care for nearly 50 Protected Wrecks off England's coast. Collaborating Organisations include several 3rd sector organisations: the Maritime Archaeology Trust, the Nautical Archaeology Society, and the Mary Rose Trust, each of which hold collections in their own right; and two industrial collaborators – a marine heritage consultancy, Fjodr, and a marine commercial archaeology organisation, Wessex Archaeology.

4. Context

Recent increased challenges stemming from climate change, offshore renewables, fishing rights, border control and Brexit, along with opportunities relating to tourism, regeneration and wellbeing have seen a renewed focus on the nature and sustainable management of UK coastal waters. The UN Ocean Decade 2021-30 strategy (Societal Outcome 6) seeks '*an accessible ocean with open and equitable access to data, information and technology and innovation*'. The maritime past is crucial to understanding and engaging with these issues, making it an optimal time for this project. Alongside professionals and researchers, marine heritage retains great popular interest. Although submerged heritage is difficult for people to visit and engage with, public interest is very high. Visitor numbers to museums are considerable (in 2019, 2.9m visits to NMM, 1.1m visits to National Museum of the Royal Navy; 837k visits to Merseyside Maritime Museum, and 327k visits to HMS *Belfast*); it formed 12 of Historic England's top 100 news stories since 2015. Management of the marine historic environment is problematic in the UK, as the agencies responsible do not have comprehensive integrated datasets of the location and nature of these assets, while the exploitation of the seas is rapidly accelerating. UK maritime heritage research frameworks note unconscious bias towards a terrestrial view of the seas as limiting cultural activity rather than driving it. Lack of accessibility and connectivity between marine collections actively militates against attempts at redress of this issue.

UNPATH builds on existing progress. Aggregators such as ADS, MEDIN, the MMO, and national Historic Environment Records provide a core for marine collections, as do archival connectors (e.g. TNA). However, they are limited in what they aggregate, are incomplete and currently incompatible. Furthermore, aggregated is not synonymous with interoperable, limiting insights that can be gained from these resources. As such, there is a firm foundation, but one which urgently requires strategic support to realise its potential. Previous (excellent) attempts, such as the EU-funded NAVIS and Pericles databases to aggregate marine data, were not embedded in national infrastructures and thus unsustainable. The benefits of this project's success will be enjoyed by: **environmental and heritage management organisations**, as the base data for informed decisions in marine development and conservation will be transformed, allowing stretched resources to be more effectively targeted, and de-risking exploitation for industry; **research communities**, as the synergistic value of multiple integrated collections permits far greater insight and impact in proportion to research investment; and, most importantly, **the public**, as co-design and co-creation of access and content enable new narratives and evolve new appreciations of significance. Consequent benefits will be measurable through enhanced online and in-person tourist visits to the UK's marine heritage, and in leadership exemplars to international marine heritage bodies.

Revelations of research potential, demonstrated through the sample marine WPs, will provide clear pointers for future research infrastructure investment priorities which will repay investment rapidly in terms of research integration and collaboration. Advancement of search and access techniques have considerable potential to empower communities to contribute to research collaboration in meaningful ways, integrating private collections which are now almost entirely inaccessible.

5. Project Design and Methodologies

The design of the project is linear overall: we envisage an **Incubator Lab** in the first half of the programme where we discover, aggregate and characterise, develop search and access tools, and set the research basis for the three marine themes. The project then moves into an **Innovation Lab**, where we apply the tools in real-world scenarios to test feasibility, resolve barriers, then employ these outputs to explore genuine innovation in co-design and co-creation capability to

permit consumption, enhancement and evolution of the connected collections through visualisation, immersion and exhibition engagement. **Impact Delivery**, the final phase, will complete the work's evaluation and development of the formal documentation and final reporting outputs.

The seven **Work Packages** will progress through these three phases, with iterative connections to ensure that lessons learned within one WP can be transmitted quickly to other WPs, providing robust course-correction flexibility. This design also ensures that the project RAs, and in particular the ECRs, benefit from a full spectrum viewpoint and see their roles within the context of the entire programme. Further, this design integrates insights from industrial, 3rd sector and heritage management organisations at each step of the project to ensure real-world applicability.

WP1 will lead a partner data structure survey; and survey of existing data infrastructures, feeding development of the UNPATH core metadata model and core data standards (e.g. vocabularies and recording practices). It will enhance existing portals with aggregation of UK marine data (national bodies – Coflein, Canmore, Heritage Gateway; ADS ArchSearch; MEDIN, ARIADNE); and build upon work done by ADS in the EU-funded VENUS project to provide up-to-date data standards guidance in the ADS Open Access world-renowned Guides to Good Practice.

WP2 will trial Natural Language Processing (NLP) and computer vision-based enhancement and segmentation of sparse data; undertake audience/stakeholder behaviour/engagement analysis (defining search and discovery ontologies); deliver enhancement of sparse data across core datasets arising from WP1, and develop UNPATH search tools (text, image, sound, space, time) for application to enhanced collections, enable 'free-association' search beyond core datasets, and test machine learning to assist searches and linkages.

WP3.1 will deliver four strands. (i) Dissolve boundaries between museum-based *Mary Rose* and *Holland 1* and the still-submerged *Holland 5*, *Mary Rose* and *The Needles* Protected Wrecks and adjacent non-protected wrecks, to explore how conflict or trade vessels connect individuals and coastal communities; relating to construction, provisions, ordnance, crews, health, rescue and display; (ii) develop digital connectors linking disparate wreck artefact and archival collections; (iii) explore potential applications of *Holland 1/5* real-time immersive digital experiences through XR; (iv) map the cultural and social attributes of the wrecks with contemporary communities, values and debates. These will be used to develop innovative co-designed, co-created wreck audience engagement and learning tools and packages and prototype connectors, enabling a range of consumers (Protected Wrecks Association, museum partners, wreck divers, volunteers, researchers, school/university students and the public) to interact with and potentially enhance connected collections.

WP3.2 will identify relevant maritime collections and data sets required to support wreck identification, to be tested on a sample of problematic wreck sites. A documentary and data tagging initiative will be developed by creating a search criteria classification system designed to link key relevant historical collections and data. In addition, a site characterisation and classification approach will also be constructed, linking marine collections and data sets and principal geological and hydrodynamical processes and associated biological conditions to create a mechanism to evaluate likely condition and survival trajectories. The two protocols will be assessed in the context of creation of appropriate adaptive management strategies, and on the applicability and relevance of this approach at a wider UK and International scale.

WP3.3 will create a computer simulation to combine a variety of data sources to facilitate public access to Doggerland. Sources are disparate in spatial scale, storage size and computational demand (e.g. sonar bathymetric maps, seismic profiles, publicly available archaeological collections such as CITIZAN, local HERs, ADS online library, and palaeo-environmental seabed cores). The ERC *Europe's Lost Frontier's* output (the modelled landscape at the beginning of the Holocene) will form the base. New data collections will be integrated to test and advance the simulation. The simulation's front end will allow the user to 'fast forward' from the last Ice Age, melting glaciers and changing sea level to any selected time. Through a small band of Doggerland

hunter-gatherers inhabiting the landscape at the time specified, the user can either observe or take significant decisions for the simulated community, thus accessing the data patterns of the submerged landscape via the processes which formed them. Collections will not tell the story of Doggerland but allow users to find their own stories within it.

WP4 will engage with existing audiences, find new audiences and communities and co-design the interface underpinning new ways of exploring and generating novel and unexpected narratives from data which may use multiple channels, e.g. embodied and sound-based. It will reveal user requirements and preferences for engaging with interoperable collections. It will deploy a Rapid Application Development methodology to transform requirements into new and sustainable interfaces for three case-studies, addressing specific audiences, audience requirements and three key research themes. (i) Co-design and User Generated Pathways data layer for non-coastal communities, with a focus on trading/commodities and migrant communities over time (cf WP3.1 datasets). This case study develops new audiences, engages via new interaction modes and is intended to surface unexpected, community specified, connections between the interoperable data. (ii) The visually impaired public, using spatialised audio content (e.g. derived from WP3.2 sonar datasets) to both represent and allow interrogation of interoperable datasets, and address barriers to access presented by traditional complex database interfaces. Using creative response this case study will be extended to generate novel means of engagement with wider audiences whose interest goes beyond the historic and scientific to the aesthetic, social or spiritual (qv Burra Charter); and (iii) Cross-disciplinary researchers, using natural and cultural heritage collections derived from WP3.3 simulation, allowing researchers from both natural and cultural disciplines to explore and discover connectivity between these domains. The interoperable UNPATH datasets will be made amenable to multiple modes of access through an UNPATH 'Explorer' which will be demonstrated and promoted as a web based resource, a mobile application, and an immersive VR interface (e.g. HMD) and installations evaluated and deployed via WP5.

WP5 will co-design evaluation methodologies for audiences of the products, and apply those methods to assessment of the Incubator, Innovator and Impact components of UNPATH. Following the Digital Culture Charter and informed by the digital equity methodology of D'Ignazio & Klein (2020), WP5 will begin by establishing a values framework, and associated metrics, for the project, auditing progress against the framework on an annual basis. Via audience mapping, WP5 will identify and recruit target audiences into UNPATH in Year 1, and work between them and across WPs1-4 to ensure that project outputs accommodate user needs, that the project's exhibition programme is curated for accessibility, and that inclusive evaluation methods are developed and applied across the project to accommodate neurodiverse participants. WP5 will then coordinate user evaluation activities in the Innovator and Impact phases of the project, utilising (accessible) survey, interview and automated data acquisition tools. This includes an assessment of the efficacy and inclusiveness of the co-design approach itself at the close of the Innovator Lab, and analysis and publication (with WP3&4 leads) of learning, social and emotional outcomes of audience workshops, exhibitions and other dissemination activities. WP5 will ensure delivery of a final exhibition programme, with the NMM coordinating museums partners and industrial and 3rd sector collaborating organisations to extend the reach of the project further. As above, the nature of the exhibition programme will be established in consultation with our key audience groups (including virtual and pop-up events), integrating (where possible) with existing programmes such as anniversary and thematic events. WP5 will also track the application of the research tools enhanced in the Incubator Lab across the life of the project, and map the novel interpretations, questions and research findings that emerge.

6. Project Management

WP6 covers the project management of UNPATH. PI (Sloane, Historic England) is ultimately responsible, leading a management group of the Work Package Lead Co-Is: WP1: ADS (Richards), York; WP2 Maritime Archaeology (Sturt), Southampton; WP3.1 Civil Engineering and Surveying (Coats), Portsmouth; WP3.2 Ocean Sciences (Roberts), Bangor; WP3.3 Archaeological and Forensic Sciences (Gaffney), Bradford; WP4 Simulation and Visualisation (Jeffrey), Glasgow School of Art; WP5 Research and Engagement (Perry), MOLA.

9 supporting Researcher Co-Is are working on specific elements of each work package (1 on WP1, 2 on WP2, 1 on WP3.1, 2 on WP3.2, 1 on WP4, 2 on WP5). A total of 20 Research Associates or Technicians will work on particular aspects of each WP. They are distributed as follows: WP1: 4, WP2: 1, WP3.1: 4; WP3.2: 2, WP3.3: 2, WP4: 3, WP5: 3; and WP6: 1). Many will be fixed term (1-2 years). Some will be part-time. At least 4 will be ECRs in digital humanities. Total FTE complement for the whole project over 36 months will be 33.5.

The PI will be supported by a dedicated Project Manager, and dedicated Finance, Legal and Research Office Support. Technical programme support will be via MS ProjectView linking resource management and time record tracking to project documentation libraries and funding drawdown. An online shared space will be created on Knowledge Hub or in Teams. Project communications and PR will be overseen by HE with communication protocols agreed with all contributors and AHRC to ensure coordinated release and impact assessment. Historic England (Co-I Jeffery) will coordinate the formal Partner relationships during the project and will be responsible for oversight of formal agreements with each of the Collaborating Organisations.

The management team will meet regularly (1/month) and the entire consortium will also meet regularly virtually, to ensure programme oversight and inter-connection during each phase and provide opportunities for rapid course correction as interim research outcomes emerge.

An Advisory Board will meet twice yearly to review progress and provide advice. Members are: Maria Economou (Glasgow University); Ian Murphy (Liverpool Museums); Ian Oxley (former English Heritage); Martijn Manders (Dutch Cultural Heritage Agency); Chris Graham (Marine Management Organisation); Kate Roberts (Cadw); and Rebecca Bailey (TaNC) as an observer for AHRC.

Using HE's Public Value Framework, WP6 will assess potential impacts of the project's outputs on its core beneficiaries: environmental and heritage organisations – including evidence of use in informed decision making; evidence of increased use of associated resources of UNPATH partners (e.g. CITIZAN app; Mary Rose visits); research communities – including evidence of application to current marine heritage management, evidence of materialisation of novel research agendas; and assessment of value to Early Career Researchers.

7. Dissemination and Outputs

Key products and outputs will be created throughout the lifetime of the project:

1. Report on infrastructure options and metadata standard(s) and guidance for marine data
2. Enhanced shared infrastructure and portals for marine heritage management in the UK
3. Delivery of new marine data via European and national marine e-infrastructures (ARIADNE & MEDIN)
4. Digital archive for all project data outputs
5. Publication on NLP and computer vision enhancement of sparse data across GLAM and heritage agency collections
6. Research reports on the three test areas (enhancing significance of submerged and displayed wrecks and their collections; identification, and sustainability, of wreck sites; simulation of submerged palaeolandscapes)
7. Sustainable co-designed co-created with multiple audiences and fully evaluated suite of multi-modal interfaces (i.e. online, mobile, installation) built on a core immersive system.
8. Inclusive exhibition programme designed and delivered for underserved target audiences at museum sites, in communities and digitally delivered.
9. Values and accountability metrics for UNPATH
10. Publication on audience outcomes of UNPATH explorer and its dissemination versions
11. Code publication via GitHub
12. Updated marine Guide to Good Practice at ADS
13. Final project report with impact evaluation and options appraisal for future direction of travel